

Carvajal Syndrome : A New Case with Additional Dermatological Features

Hajar Moata¹, Fouzia Hali¹, Fatima Maarouf^{2,3}, Hind Dehbi^{2,3}, Soumiya Chiheb¹

¹Department of dermatology and venerology. Ibn Rochd University Hospital. Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy. University Hassan II. Casablanca. Morocco.

²Medical Genetics Laboratory, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco.

³Cellular and Molecular Pathology Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Hassan II University, Casablanca, Morocco.

Dear editor ,

Carvajal syndrome is a rare hereditary disease, stemming from a recessive mutation in the desmoplakin gene, crucial for cell adhesion. Its hallmark features include woolly hair, palmoplantar keratoderma, and dilated cardiomyopathy, primarily affecting the left ventricle of the heart ¹. We report the case of an 18-month-old infant early diagnosed with Carvajal syndrome revealed by dermatological symptoms and confirmed by genetic testing.

An 18-month-old girl, born to first-degree Moroccan consanguineous parents, was admitted for palmoplantar hyperkeratotic lesions. A similar symptomatology was reported in her twin paternal aunts (figure1). Clinical examination revealed bilateral palmoplantar keratoderma with focal hyperkeratotic and crusted lesions on palms, associated to blisters and crusted erosions on both lower limbs .The patient also presented woolly and scarce aspect of

hair involving the entire scalp and eyebrows and thick, white, and dystrophic fingernails (figure 2). No facial dysmorphism was noted . Cardiovascular and pleuropulmonary examinations were without abnormalities. Genetic testing was performed. Whole exome sequencing (WES) revealed the presence of a pathogenic variant (NM_ 004415.4: c.7097G>A ; p.Arg2366His*) homozygous for the *desmoplakin* (DSP) gene. Dermatological manifestations ,including palmoplantar keratoderma and woolly aspect of hair, associated to a mutation of the DSP gene led to the diagnosis of Carvajal syndrome. An electrocardiogram and a two dimensionnal echocardiography were performed showing no cardiac abnormalities. Regular cardiac monitoring is planned for our patient, to detect the onset of dilated cardiomyopathy at an early stage. A parental segregation study has been proposed, as they are probably heterozygous carriers.

Figure 1 : Family pedigree of the patient

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Figure 2 : (a,b) Woolly and scarce aspect of hair, (c,d) palmoplantar keratoderma with focal hyperkeratotic and crusted lesions on palms, (e) Thick,white, and dystrophic fingernails ,(f) Blisters and crusted erosions on both lower limbs

Carvajal syndrome is a cardiocutaneous affection considered as a rare variant of Naxos disease, which has the same cutaneous phenotype but a predominantly right ventricular involvement¹. Characteristic dermatological features include woolly hair at birth and palmoplantar keratosis occurring during the first year of life². Blisters and nail involvement, seen in our patient, are unusual in Carvajal syndrome. To our knowledge, these additional dermatological features have only been reported in five cases of NAXOS-Carvajal syndrome³. This syndrome is secondary to homozygous mutation in the gene coding for desmoplakin, the essential component of desmosomes which are tough and strong intercellular junctions, particularly abundant in the epidermis and myocardium, which explains the characteristic symptoms of the syndrome⁴. The unfavorable prognosis of Carvajal syndrome is mainly related to an early onset of the cardiac manifestations, rapidly progressive dilatation of the cardiac chambers and high risk of sudden cardiac death⁵. In our case, the dermatological manifestations revealed the diagnosis at an early age, before the onset of cardiac symptoms, enabling regular monitoring of our patient to reduce the risk of morbidity and mortality due to cardiac failure.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Conflict of interest: None.

Funding source: None

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